

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D1.5 Strategy for addressing the Ethics, M18

27/02/2025

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D1.5 – Strategy for addressing the Ethics, M6

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ABS	Access and Benefit-Sharing
ABSCH	Access and Benefit-Sharing Clearing House
AIS	Artificial Intelligence System
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CITES	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data protection Officer
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
DUC	Demonstrator Use Case
EC	European Commission
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EMO BON	European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network
ETN	European Tracking Network
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
MPA	Marine Protected Area
NCP	National Contact Point
NFP	National Focal Point
NP	Nagoya Protocol
PMT	Project Management Team
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The DTO-BioFlow project aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. The project is organised around five main topics, one per Work Package (WP) these being: identification and creation of an inventory of “sleeping” biodiversity data, as well as mobilisation of data from data providers (WP2); development of sustained data flows of new biodiversity data types (including genomic data, plankton imaging data, biologging and passive acoustic data, among others, in WP3); demonstration of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring developing policy relevant-use cases (WP4); realisation of the data products developed in all the other WPs into the DTO infrastructure, ensuring interoperability and scalability (WP5); and communicating, disseminating and bringing the work developed into the relevant user communities (WP6). Due to the work developed within each of these components, it was foreseen that an ethics strategy should be developed to identify potential issues and the procedures to follow up for each activity where ethical considerations are needed.

A first ‘Strategy for addressing the Ethics’ (D1.5) was developed by the Ethics Advisor of the project (Dr. Barbier), based on the issues identified in the Grant Agreement and supported by meetings with the individual WPs. A revision of the strategy is due on months 18 and 42.

The Strategy identifies the following main ethical issues relevant to the work of DTO-BioFlow:

1. **Human participation and personal data protection in EU & non-EU countries:** the involvement of stakeholders and end-users, including civil society, implies human participation and the protection of personal data, in both EU and non-EU countries.
2. **The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) methodologies,** or digital models development particularly in decision-making tools must be robust. The system must guarantee human oversight, define uncertainty and ensure transparency about the limitation of the tool, explicability, and avoid bias.
3. **The use and integration of genetic data in the project and its respective compliance with the Nagoya Protocol** and the new High Seas Treaty regarding biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction or with other relevant international/European conventions must meet the requirements designed with respect to access and benefit sharing.
4. **The use and integration of genetic data and its respective compliance with CITES** when species are identified as endangered.
5. Certain tasks could raise **safety/security issues** that would need to be discussed and managed to ensure compliance with national legislation (for example, the underwater imaging system to be deployed or the acoustic equipment).
6. The **tagging of new fish species** which requires ethics approval and **the integration of data collected from tagged animals** for which the data provider must confirm that an ethics approval has been obtained.
7. Informed and **responsible social media use** – misinformation and disinformation.

The current version of the ‘Strategy for Addressing the Ethics’ on month 18 (D1.6) follows discussions and meetings between the Ethics Advisor and the WP leaders during the 1st General Assembly on 1st October 2024. During these meetings, existing knowledge, standards, and guidelines were shared to help scientists meet ethical requirements at European and international level if/where applicable. All WP leads were requested to complete an ethics self-assessment form, provided by the Ethics Advisor to inform the development of the next version of the DTO-BioFlow Ethics Strategy. To evaluate the current Strategy and advised methodology, an ethics-self assessment for each WP has been produced in November 2024 to:

1. Assess how the scientists have appropriated good practices.
2. Identify bottlenecks.
3. Identify the next research activities for each WP.

The current report based on the ethics self-assessment informs the updates required to the strategy plan for the next period.

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1. Background

The DTO-BioFlow Grant Agreement (GA) and Work Plan foresaw the need for an External Ethics Advisor to develop a Strategy for Addressing the Ethics to ensure the consortium's compliance with best practices. This document was foreseen as a project deliverable to be delivered in month 6, and reviewed and updated in months 18 and 42.

A document describing the Terms of Reference for the activities and offer required for the project was made available to potential candidates, following the internal subcontracting procedures and regulations of the coordinating partner, the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ), who acted as contractor for the advisor. As a result of the procedure, Dr Michelle Barbier was contracted to act as Ethics Advisor of the project and to develop the Strategy for Addressing the Ethics in consultation with the project partners.

The Ethics Advisor developed a first document 'Strategy for Addressing the Ethics' (D1.5) as the first of three versions, with updates to be delivered at Months 18 and 42 (D1.6 and D1.7).

This report is an update of the 'Strategy for addressing the Ethics' (D1.6) to be delivered at M18.

2. Introduction

The HORIZON EUROPE DTO-BioFlow project aims to bring "sleeping" and new types of biodiversity data into the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), and to demonstrate an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring developing policy relevant-use cases to contribute to this digital knowledge system. Combining sustained data flows, models and new algorithms, DTO-BioFlow will develop and integrate the biological component of the DTO, including new digital tools and services.

The project will advance the collection, harmonisation, accessibility, and analysis of marine biodiversity relevant data, the integration of these data and analytical tools into DTO architectures, and the applicability of a functioning DTO biodiversity component to address policy-relevant use cases. The project includes seven policy-relevant use cases (demonstrators) to demonstrate the benefit of continuous data streams for marine ecosystem management.

3. Ethics issues

As detailed in the deliverable D5.1, the project raises several ethical issues.

The Strategy identifies the following main ethical issues relevant to the work of DTO-BioFlow:

1. **Human participation and personal data protection in EU & non-EU countries:** the involvement of stakeholders and end-users, including civil society, implies human participation and the protection of personal data, in both EU and non-EU countries.
2. **The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI)/Machine Learning (ML) methodologies,** or digital models development particularly in decision-making tools must be robust. The system must guarantee human oversight, define uncertainty and ensure transparency about limitation of the tool, explicability, and avoid bias.
3. **The use and integration of genetic data in the project and its respective compliance with the Nagoya Protocol** and the new High Seas Treaty regarding biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction or with other relevant international/European conventions must meet the requirements designed with respect to access and benefit sharing.
4. **The use and integration of genetic data and its respective compliance with CITES** when species are identified as endangered.

5. Certain tasks could raise **safety/security issues** that would need to be discussed and managed to ensure compliance with national legislation (for example, the underwater imaging system to be deployed or the use of acoustic equipment).
6. The **tagging of new fish species** which requires ethics approval and **the integration of data collected from tagged animals** for which the data provider must confirm that an ethics approval has been obtained.
7. Informed and **responsible social media use** – misinformation and disinformation.

Discussions were held with leaders of all Work Packages during the General Assembly on 1st October 2024, followed by a meeting after the revised version of the Ethics Strategy was produced.

The summary of the ethical issues identified by WP and by task is presented in Table 1.

4. Methodology

The methodology has been developed and followed as described in D1.5.

Since then, the ethics advisor met all the WP leaders during the General Assembly (1st October 2024) and attended all WP presentations. Afterwards, each WP (WP1, 2, 3, 4, and 5) was asked to complete an ethics self-assessment provided by the Ethics Advisor. These documents were analysed to update the Strategy on Addressing the Ethics and are part of this report.

Table 1: Summary of the ethical issues identified by WP and by task (in blue: ethics issues discussed with the WP leaders, in green: discussion pending with WP leaders).

Work Package	Task	Task Leader (WP Lead)	Activity	Ethical Considerations	Ethics Actions
WP1 Project Management	1.4	VLIZ	Data Management Plan	Must include personal data collection, storage and processing protection (GDPR Compliance - list of DPOs or data protection policies) established and monitored	DPO established and data sharing routines documents in DMP - GDPR Compliance
WP2 Increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data	2.1/2.3	CIIMAR	Inventory and analysis of defining frameworks for biodiversity monitoring/ Identified gaps and shortcomings/ Protected, endangered & threatened species (PETS) abundance	Risk of identification (and thus potentially subsequent activities on) of sleeping genetic data that is not compliant with NP/ABS (EEZ/UN treaty on high seas) or with CITES	Identification of cleared data regarding NP to follow ABS actions and compliance / CITES restrictions. Data may be identified, but we will not mobilise all the data sources identified (only the data from the data calls in particular, where it is required full compliance). The 2 nd call is ongoing and will ensure that the data sources are compliant with these regulations
	2.4	ICES	Identifying existing barriers and develop pathways for sustained access	NP/CITES/UN treaty on high seas	Provide legal information to ensure compliance
	2.5	VLIZ	Organise open calls to data holders + data holder workshop	Consideration of genetic data compliance with NP/CITES/UN treaty on High Seas, with additional issues regarding Human participation and personal data collection (compliance with GDPR) Ownership of scientific data	Ensure ABS and CITES compliance, DPO to ensure protection of personal data Ensure that the ownership policy is described and clear in the information sheets, and implement certain “return activities” (benefit-sharing actions) for them
WP3 Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO	3.1	HCMR	Building the biodiversity component with plankton and ARMS genomic observation networks Plus potential engagement of citizen scientists for water sample collection	Compliance with NP/CITES/UN treaty on high seas/ with additional issues regarding human participation and personal data collection (GDPR)	Ensure ABS & CITES compliance, if surveys or direct stakeholder engagement, make sure that informed consent is applied. If needed, list of DPO or data protection policies

	3.2	SU	Use of plankton imaging underwater instruments (camera, etc.)	Potential national security issue underwater image recording	Might require authorisation from certain countries (i.e. France)
	3.3	EV INBO	Use of biologging sensors	Potential National security issue. Also, potential issue of real-time data providing information on geolocation of threatened or endangered species	Check the need of authorisation from certain countries Draft a policy regarding real-time access data, if real-time data is produced
WP4 Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases the benefit of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring	4.1	UGOT	DUC-1: DTO-BioFlow demonstration for invasive species management. DUC-2: DTO-BioFlow for adaptive offshore construction and energy harvesting. DUC-3: DTO-BioFlow for assessment of plankton diversity in relation to human impact. DUC-4: DTO-BioFlow for spatial planning of sustainable mariculture. DUC-5: DTO-BioFlow for MPA design and marine spatial planning. DUC-6: DTO-BioFlow for low impact fisheries. DUC-7: DTO-Bioflow for Ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration	End users/stakeholders' engagement implies human participation and protection of personal data. Models to be used to develop a decision-support tools for policy makers Potentially AI	Informed consent for all stakeholder participation; Data Management Plan for collecting, storing and processing all personal information; verification on non-EU countries requirements. Trustworthy AI systems. Models should be verified and validated. Transparency should be assured considering uncertainty and bias.
	4.3	VLIZ	Creation of new knowledge using the digital solutions to represent reality and forecast future scenarios	Models to be used to develop a decision-support tools for policy makers	Trustworthy AI systems. Models should be verified and validated. Transparency should be assured considering uncertainty and bias
	4.4	SINTEF	Delivery of evidence-based knowledge in support of policymaking and implementation		
WP5 Integration in DTO infrastructure	5.1	TNO	Supporting operationalized data streams & demonstrators by creating digital tools & services	Potentially AI	Trustworthy AI systems
	5.2	SINTEF	Interoperability, compatibility & aligning with DTO & other initiatives		

WP6 Communication, Exploitation & Dissemination	6.2	EMBRC ERIC	Bringing in the Biodiversity Data Provider perspective: Pathways towards sustaining the flow of data into the EU DTO framework	End users/stakeholders' engagement and workshops require human participation Onboarding kit will share personal information	Informed consent for all stakeholder participation; Ensure consent for use of name, image or likeness of video participants; Informed consent for all stakeholders' participation; DMP for collecting, storing and processing all personal information; verification on non-EU countries requirements
	6.3	TRUST-IT	Bringing in the User perspective in support of Mission Ocean	The campaign "User Uptake of DTO Outputs"/ consult with key stakeholder groups: matchmaking events & workshops; Potential risk of misinformation on social media.	Awareness of risk of misinformation on social media
	6.4	GEOMAR	International cooperation & best practices and support to the UN Ocean Decade	Ensure data privacy	Ensure GDPR compliance standards for newsletter subscription, including opt-out
	6	TRUST-IT	Video	Personal information including use of name, image or likeness	Ensure consent for use of name, image or likeness of video participants Informed consent for all stakeholder participation; Data Management Plan for collecting, storing and processing all personal information; verification on non-EU countries requirements

5. Analysis of the WPs

5.1. WP1 – Project Management & WP6 Communication, Exploitation & Dissemination

The main concern in WP1 is the collection of personal data/cookies from the website and the creation of newsletter.

The website and newsletter of DTO-BioFlow are part of WP6 (Communication, dissemination, and exploitation). The details of the privacy policy of VLIZ are described on the website <https://www.vliz.be/nl/privacy>.

Host institution responsible for collecting and processing personal data must provide details of the data protection officer or experts managing data			
Institution	WP	Name of DPO (or generic designation)	Email of DPO/data controller
VLIZ	WP1	R. T'J.	privacy@vliz.be
Trust-IT	WP1	Data controller regarding all personal data processing carried out through the Website	privacy-dto-bioflow@trust-itservices.com

The WP will continue the same activities.

The same recommendations provided in D5.1 apply if new websites or newsletters are developed.

5.2. WP2 – Increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data

The objectives of WP2 are to analyse the biodiversity data landscape towards identifying data that is necessary (but currently missing) to enable a functioning DTO to support the EU to deliver on its biodiversity goals. Relevant sleeping data sources will be assessed and prioritised for ingestion based on identified criteria, including the impact of the missing data on a functioning DTO.

In addition, online surveys have been organised, as well as workshops.

5.2.1. WP2 – summarised activities

Research activities undertaken with human research participants, WP2	Organisation	WP/task
Internal DTO-BioFlow Survey: Input to the biodiversity data pathways barriers Playbook. The D2.2 deliverable (first version of the Barrier Playbook) required input from a wide range of internal stakeholders. Results from similar recent surveys were used as a baseline and then more focused input from the DTO-BioFlow Consortium partners was requested.	ICES	T2.2
Data providers workshop, Spring 2024. The workshop trained new data providers (data grant recipients) in the formats, and technical aspects of providing their dataflows according to the agreement in the data grant provision.	EMBRC-ERIC	T2.5

Organisations selected under the first DTO-BioFlow Data call (2023, T2.5)	Country	WP/task
<i>Bangor University School of Ocean Sciences</i>	UK	T2.5
<i>Futurismo Azores Adventures Portugal</i>	Portugal	T2.5
<i>Institute of Polar Sciences, National Research Council (ISP-CNR)</i>	Italy	T2.5
<i>Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research</i>	Israël	T2.5

Menter Môn	UK	T2.5
National Oceanography Centre	UK	T2.5
Nord University	Norway	T2.5
stichting ANEMOON	The Netherlands	T2.5
Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute	Sweden	T2.5

The procedures to identify the research participants were clearly defined. The assessment process conducted by VLIZ (Task 2.5) applied during the 2023 DTO-BioFlow Data call is available at <https://dto-bioflow.eu/marine-biodiversity-data-open-call>

The second call now requires the data holders to confirm the compliance of the data with all legislation (CITES/NP/ABS etc.)

At ICES, the purpose of Task 2.5 was to have at least one response from each DTO-Bioflow partner; all partners were contacted and responded.

Both VLIZ and ICES confirmed that an information sheet has been distributed to all research participants for Task 2.5 and informed consent forms have been obtained from all research participants and are digitally stored. Both institutions provided the names and email address of their Data Protection Officers.

They confirmed that personal data were protected. Results were shown as aggregated graphs/statistics; text quotes were used without attribution to subject and checked that no inference to the subject could be made.

5.2.2. Future activities M18-M36 and recommendations

No further activities engaging stakeholders are planned for the next period in WP2.

Two institutions selected under the 1st DTO-BioFlow call are from Norway and UK, non-EU countries, but where GDPR is applicable. This should not raise issues.

However, one of the institutions selected under the 1st DTO BioFlow call is the Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research from Israel. Compliance with GDPR must be ensured.

Recommendations

The consortium must ensure that the transfer of personal data from Israel is compliant with GDPR. See with your DPO.

Furthermore, more and more *“universities are seeking official guidance from the European Commission as they struggle to assess whether Israeli institutions are still eligible to join Horizon Europe projects, as the Israeli war against Hamas is raising ethical questions across academia”*¹.

Recommendations

The coordinator should contact the DTO-BioFlow Project Officer at the European Commission to ensure the full compliance of research activities with Israel.

Existing barriers to data flow into the DTO will be analysed to identify and inform on best practice and the outcomes of these analyses will be implemented with data calls, grants and access arrangements making previously inaccessible data available to the DTO. Finally, this task will inform on future EU biodiversity monitoring priorities and needs.

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¹ <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/horizon-europe/commission-under-pressure-give-guidance-rd-collaboration-israel>

Recommendations

Even if the ethical issues detailed in D1.5 do not apply directly to WP2, it is essential that the important recommendations are applied to the identified barriers such as Nagoya Protocol/ABS regulation or CITES compliance and use of data obtained from tagged fish (recommendations available in D1.5 and below).

5.3. WP3 - Concept Demonstration - summarised activities

Many ethical issues have been identified in WP3 (see D1.5) and are summarized below:

Task	Task Leader	Activity	Ethical Considerations	Ethics Actions
3.1	HCMR	Building the biodiversity component with plankton and ARMS genomic observation networks Plus potential engagement of citizen scientists for water sample collection	Compliance with NP/CITES/UN treaty on high seas/ with additional issues regarding human participation and personal data collection (GDPR) Ownership of scientific data	Ensure ABS & CITES compliance, if surveys or direct stakeholder engagement, make sure that informed consent is applied. If needed, list of DPO or data protection policies Ensure that the ownership policy is described and clear in the information sheets, and implement certain “return activities” (benefit-sharing actions) for them
3.2	SU	Use of plankton imaging underwater instruments (camera, etc.)	Potential national security issue underwater image recording	Might require authorisation from certain countries
3.3	EV INBO	Use of biologging sensors	Potential National security issue Also, potential issue of real-time data providing information on geolocation of threatened or endangered species	Check the need of authorisation from certain countries No real time data are collected
3.5	UNESCO	Citizen science data	Human participation and personal data collection (GDPR) and proper attribution of the data according to the licences and specifications set by data the creators and publishers of the data	For the citizen-based observations, we need to ensure the acknowledgement of their contributions according to the specifications set in the licenses, while preserving their privacy (GDPR compliance). Guidance on how to manage personal data can be provided by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) Ensure that the ownership policy is described and clear in the information sheets, and implement

				certain “return activities” (benefit-sharing actions) for them
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5.3.1. Compliance with Access and benefit Sharing Regulation/Nagoya Protocol

The different activities conducted during the first 18 months are detailed below:

Institution providing access to genetic data	Country where samples were collected	Institution conducting the analysis + country	Compliance with Nagoya Protocol or ABS regulation?
MGnify / EMBL-EBI (UK) - eDNA data from plankton and ARMS samples	Several EU countries, UK and Russian Federation	MGnify / EMBL-EBI (UK)	Samples are subject to the Nagoya protocol. Unclear if they are compliant or not. For samples collected in the framework of long-term time series observatories, the responsible people from each observatory will be contacted to identify the compliance of the samples or not.
OBIS - Taxonomic occurrences derived from eDNA data from plankton and ARMS samples	Several EU countries, UK and Israel (Red Sea)	OBIS	The samples from the ARMS-MBON network are compliant with the ABS regulations.
SBDI ASV portal (Sweden) - Taxonomic occurrences derived from eDNA data from plankton and ARMS samples	Sweden	SBDI ASV portal (Sweden)	Samples are subject to the Nagoya protocol. Unclear if they are compliant or not.
MGnify / EMBL-EBI (UK) - eDNA data from citizen science surveys	Several countries across the globe	MGnify / EMBL-EBI (UK)	Some of the samples are subject to the Nagoya protocol, some will be subject to BBNJ. Unclear if they are compliant or not.

Certain genetic (eDNA) data that will be analysed in the framework of DTO-BioFlow and will be included in the DTO Data Lake, have been derived from global sampling campaigns such as the Tara Oceans, the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD), the Global Ocean Sampling Expedition and the Malaspina-2010 expedition. This is necessary as such data provide an additional level of information on the distribution of non-indigenous species (NIS). Inevitably, data from global sampling campaigns have been derived from samples collected across the world, so the information of EEZ and whether samples are subject to ABS/BBNJ must be assessed on a sample-by-sample basis and not on a project basis.

Recommendations

For genetic data obtained from samples for which compliance with the ABS regulation is unclear and for samples collected in the framework of long-term time series observatories:

- Contact the responsible people from each observatory and **ask them to confirm** the compliance of the samples or not with ABS regulation. (The samples collected during the Ocean Sampling Day and during Tara expeditions are known to (should be) be compliant with ABS regulation).

For samples collected in areas beyond national jurisdiction, as the treaty of the sea is not yet implemented, it is not expected to be compliant.

5.3.2. Integration of data from endangered species/CITES compliance

Biologging data of European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) which is currently available in the European Tracking Network (ETN) will be made openly available. Only already open datasets will be made public via EMODnet and towards the DTO Data Lake.

Potentially European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) and twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*) will also be tagged within the context of the project (still pending final decision of choice of species). All the fish individuals tagged are released back into the environment where they were caught, as agreed and detailed in the respective tagging licenses approved by the relevant Ethical Committees, which are in order prior to the start of tagging activities.

In case data are obtained from samples collected on endangered species,	
Institution	EV INBO
Where will be collected the samples?	EU (Belgium)
Did you obtain an ethics approval?	Approval undergoing review by the Ethics Committee.
Is the staff trained for such activity?	Yes
Do you need authorisations according to CITES?	No, there is no trading or collection of samples from the animals

5.3.3. Human participation

Research activities undertaken with human research participants	Specify the institution organising the activity
The ICM-CSIC team is developing a test case using broadband recorders (i.e. AudioMoth) by the citizen science community participating in cetaceans' research in the North-western Mediterranean Sea (linked with Task 3.5.1 Citizen science).	The organisation involved are the ICM-CSIC (which is the research centre facilitating the protocols and analysing the data, and which is directly involved in the DTO-BioFlow project), in collaboration with: 1) Associació Cetàcea, and 2) Proyecto Vellella, which are the entities organising the activity and directly involved with the citizens.

The test case carried out by the ICM-CSIC will serve to explore if broadband recorders provided by CSIC can identify, with reasonable certainty, positive detections from the different species of cetaceans inhabiting the North-western Mediterranean Sea, where there are various species of interest.

If the test case is successful, and if the employed method is citable and replicable, the protocols and methodologies used will be promoted in the wider citizen science community. Thus, filling the gap of openly available cetacean acoustic data in the area.

Identification of organisations involved in the test case are	
ICM-CSIC (DTO-BioFlow partner)	Spain

Associació Cetàcea	Spain
Proyecto Velella	Spain
HCMR	Greece
CIBIO	Portugal

Additional organisations will be involved soon, as organisation of activities is still underway. The list is not yet complete.

Engagement of Citizen scientists				
Research activities	How many citizens?	Did you explain safety measures?	Country	WP/task
Boat surveys used for photo-identification surveys and acoustic surveys are being planned for the future (with the Hydrophones provided by the ICM-CSIC).	In the first phase, around 15 citizens.	No. The organisations in charge of explaining the safety measures and the code of conduct are the ones organising the boat surveys (at present Associació Cetàcea and Associació Velella).	Spain.	3.5.1
Sampling campaigns for collection of sediment and water samples.	Still to be determined, no information available currently.	No information available currently.	No information available currently.	3.1

The organisations involved in the test case are already working with volunteers, citizen scientists, researchers, etc., in the area. Various meetings and coordination actions took place between ICM-CSIC (DTO-BioFlow Partner) and the organisations involved to ensure the development of the test case.

Recording protocols, methodologies and data analysis are the responsibility of the CSIC. While safety measures (in relation to volunteers and staff) and code of conduct (in relation to marine fauna) are the responsibility of the entities organizing the boat surveys (at present Associació Cetacea and Velella project).

Informed Consent and information sheet	
Confirm that an information sheet has been distributed to all research participants for this task?	No.
Confirm that a signed informed consent form has been obtained from all research participants and is digitally stored.	Not yet, engagement is still to take place.
For citizen science activities, confirm that safety and security rules have been explained	Not yet, safety measures (in relation to volunteers and staff) and code of conduct (in relation to marine fauna) are the responsibility of the entities organizing the boat surveys (at present Cetacea and Velella project).

5.3.4. Personal data protection

In Task T3.5.1, Citizen Science Data will involve some personal data related to the iNaturalist and eBird platform datasets. Both platforms include terms and conditions referring to the processing of personal information, nonetheless the data is not directly collected by the project from the users, but directly from the platforms, in which it is already open data. eBird [Privacy Policy](#) and INaturalist [Privacy Policy](#).

5.3.5. Biologging

One of the objectives is to develop novel modelling of the movements of fish based on electronic tags recording environmental data, i.e. Data Storage Tags (DST), or based on acoustic tags. The specifics still need to be determined within the project. No new animals will be tagged for this purpose.

However, some tagging activities will be conducted on fish.

Host institution responsible for tagging	
Institution	EV INBO.
Which species are you tagging?	Species still need to be determined. Candidates at the moment include European eel (<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>) and twaite shad (<i>Alosa fallax</i>).
What kind of tag?	Data storage tags or acoustic tags (still to be determined).
Where will be collected the samples?	EU (Belgium).
Did you obtain an ethics approval?	Ethics approval is under review, no license number is available yet.
Is the staff trained for such activity?	Yes.
Do you need authorisations according to CITES?	No, there is no trading or collection of samples from the animals.

Recommendation for data obtained from existing data collected from tagged fish:

- Contact the data providers to ask them to confirm they obtained an ethics approval for these experiments.

Recommendation for tagging new fish species, details are provided below but to summarise, an Ethics approval must be obtained.

5.3.6. Other ethics issues: communication on social media, release of data in real time, citizen science and ownership of scientific data

The project does not collect and share any data in real time (not for any taxon). Mammal data only comes from Movebank, a platform in which data is updated already with a delay. Only the datasets that are open in Movebank are eligible to be published and made accessible on the EU DTO. The same applies for fish biologging data coming from ETN.

Publications in social media, the newsletter or any other type of news are agreed between the communications team involved and the scientists taking part in the research activities to ensure that the messages reflect the reality and our knowledge limitations if needed. The majority of the social media communications is being done through the official social media channels of the project to increase impact. The individual partners participating in the project are re-sharing these messages within their networks. The partners are also experienced and aware of the need to publish clear and accurate messages that are informative (and limiting information that could lead to be misinterpreted), when referring to any activities that they may want to promote in their personal social media channels.

For the citizen-based observations, we need to ensure the acknowledgement of their contributions according to the specifications set in the licenses, while preserving their privacy (GDPR compliance). Guidance on how to manage personal data can be provided by the [European Citizen Science Association \(ECSA\)](#).

The ownership of scientific data must be defined before and clearly stated in the information sheets. Certain “return activities” (benefit-sharing actions) for them can also be implemented.

5.3.7. Future activities of WP3 and recommendations

5.3.7.1. Citizen science activities

HCMR and CIBIO will be organizing a citizen science campaign in the framework of the [ANERIS project](#). Citizens will be collecting water and sediment samples for eDNA metabarcoding. Details on the locations and schedule of ANERIS citizen science campaigns are to be decided by the consortium. Data produced will be included in the already identified genomics datasets by T3.1. The institutions organising the activity are HCMR (which is also a DTO-BioFlow partner) and CIBIO. For ANERIS, stakeholder engagement is vital since without it, the relevant task cannot be completed.

For ANERIS, the procedures and criteria are not available yet.

While engaging citizen science activities with external organisations

1. Ensure that the external partners engaged in these citizen activities have a clear process for engaging citizens in the research activities:

- Recruitment process defined.
- Information sheet and obtained informed consent from citizen.
- Explanation of the safety rules.
- Protection of their personal data.
- Ensure the scientific data ownership policy is clearly explained.
- Potentially some benefit sharing actions can be implemented.

2. Ensure that the external partners are collecting sediment or sea water samples for genetic (including eDNA) analysis in compliance with the Nagoya Protocol/ABS regulation. Pay specific attention for citizen activities conducted in low-middle income countries.

5.3.7.2. Integration of more genetic/eDNA data

HCMR / EMBL-EBI will be analysing genetic (eDNA) data to transform them into Darwin Core archives for their inclusion into EMODnet and the DTO.

There might be endangered or sensitive species occurrences deriving from the analysis of the genomic (eDNA) data.

Recommendations

1. For genetic data obtained from samples for which compliance with applicable the ABS regulations is unclear and for samples collected in the framework of long-term time series observatories, contact the responsible people from each observatory and **ask them to confirm the compliance of the samples** or not. (The samples collected during the Ocean Sampling Day and during Tara expeditions are known to (should be) be compliant with ABS regulation).
2. For samples collected in area beyond national jurisdiction, as the treaty of the sea is not yet implemented, no need to obtain this confirmation.

3. For data obtained from endangered or sensitive species occurrences outside the EU waters, **contact the responsible people to ask them to confirm that samples were obtained in compliance with CITES.**

5.3.7.3. Compliance with ABS regulations

The initial strategy suggested in D5.1 is still applicable:

ABS regulation:

- 1. For samples compliant with the NP/ABS regulation** (such as those available via [EMO BON](#)): start the ingestion from material sample data. The data providers should confirm the compliance.
- 2. For samples collected before the NP entered into force (2014-10-12), at EU level**, a relevant contact point at the EU level should be sought to ask if permission is needed. The integration of such data is acceptable if the origin of the data is European.
- 3. For samples collected before the NP entered into force (2014-10-12), outside of EU waters**, contact the NFP of the country in question to ask whether the consortium needs authorization to use the data. NFPs will require an explanation of the purpose of the research activities, how the data will be used, etc. **Ask if permission is needed; particular attention should be paid to low- and middle-income countries outside the EU.** The NCPs are available on the websites provided in **D1.5**.
- 4. If the origin of data/samples is unknown**, try to identify the data provider and contact/ask them to fill in a table with related information (a template is available for the partners via the MS Teams/SharePoint environment, an overview of the template information has been provided in D1.5). **If samples are coming from low- and middle-income countries, the NCPs must be contacted to get the authorization to use the data.** If the origin of the data/samples remains unknown these samples/data should not be used.

5.3.7.4. Integration of data from endangered species

The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora, known as [CITES](#), or the Washington Convention, aims to ensure that international trade in species listed in its appendices, as well as in parts and derivatives thereof, does not undermine the conservation of biodiversity and is based on the sustainable use of wild species. It concerns not only animal trade but also samples (blood, skin, etc.) for scientific purpose, collected on animals dead or alive in the high sea and in EEZ. CITES covers international trade and the EU is a single market, no permits are needed for transactions within the EU. The full text of the Convention is available [here](#).

All import, export, re-export and introduction from the sea of species covered by the Convention has to be authorized through a licensing system. Each Party to the Convention has designated one or more Management Authorities in charge of administering that licensing system and one or more Scientific Authorities to advise them on the effects of trade on the status of the species. On CITES website, information on implementation of and compliance with the Convention related to each Party to the Convention, including dependent territories is available. The purpose of [the country profiles](#) is to place all information in one place that concerns each Party, including on [designated authorities](#), reports, reservations, registers, exemptions and special procedures, stricter domestic measures and compliance status.

The species covered by CITES are listed in [three Appendices](#), according to the degree of protection they need.

Appendices I and II, III:

Appendix I includes species threatened with extinction. They are threatened with extinction and CITES prohibits international trade in specimens of these species except when the purpose of the import is not commercial

(see [Article III](#)), for instance for scientific research. In these exceptional cases, trade may take place provided it is authorized by the granting of both an import permit and an export permit (or re-export certificate).

Appendix II includes species not necessarily threatened with extinction, but in which trade must be controlled in order to avoid utilization incompatible with their survival. International trade in specimens of species listed in this Appendix is allowed only on presentation of the appropriate permits or certificates. International trade in specimens of Appendix-II species may be authorized by the granting of an export permit or re-export certificate. No import permit is necessary for these species under CITES (although a permit is needed in some countries that have taken stricter measures than CITES requires). Permits or certificates should only be granted if the relevant authorities are satisfied that certain conditions are met, above all that trade will not be detrimental to the survival of the species in the wild. (See [Article IV](#) of the Convention)

In the case of **specimens introduced from the sea**, a certificate has to be issued by the Management Authority of the State into which the specimens are being brought, for species listed in Appendix I or II. It involves specimens taken in the marine environment not under the jurisdiction of any State. For further information, see the text of the Convention, [Article III, paragraph 5](#) and [Article IV, paragraph 6](#). Introduction from the sea does not apply to Appendix-III specimens.

Appendix III contains species that are protected in at least one country, which has asked other CITES Parties for assistance in controlling the trade.

Recommendations regarding data obtained from samples from endangered species. These samples, if collected in non-EU waters and transferred to EU, must be compliant with CITES

- Identify the species and check if they are part of the Appendix I, II.
- Identify where the samples come from: EU, non EU, EEZ, high seas.
- Contact the responsible people to ensure that samples were obtained in compliance with CITES.
- Consult the CITES website if needed.
- It should be noted that in the case of eDNA analysis, if the result is a correlation with a sensitive species, the results can be shared and integrated into the DTO platform because they were obtained more than 24 hours after sampling and therefore after the potential passage of the endangered species.

5.3.7.5. Biologging

The overall recommendations for ethical and legal considerations of tagging are as follows (for any new tagging of fish).

Recommendations for new biologging activities

- Determine if tagging is appropriate.
- Consider alternative methods for addressing research questions.
- Review relevant existing data for the species and area of consideration.
- Ensure that there is a scientific or conservation justification for obtaining new data and that those data are best provided by tags.
- Follow best practices of research design.
- Develop the research plan with animal welfare as a high priority.
- Evaluate equipment options and choose the instrument and attachment that provide the data needed.
- As much as possible, ascertain required samples sizes and statistical approaches in advance, obtaining expert advice if needed.
- Tag the fewest number of individuals necessary in the least invasive and impactful manner possible to achieve the project goals.

- Prepare adequately for fieldwork.
- Conduct a thorough risk assessment in advance.
- Prepare for unexpected risks to the safety of animals and humans.
- Ensure the capture/tagging team is trained in the safe and proper procedures for boat approaches (and capture-release techniques if required) and use of tagging equipment.
- Comply with all applicable local, national and international legal requirements.
- Obtain review and approval by an animal ethics committee, even if not locally required...

Recommendation for data obtained from existing data collected through fish tagged:

- Contact the data providers to ask them to confirm they obtained an ethics approval for these experimentations.

5.3.7.6. Deployment of Instrument at sea

An acoustic low-cost sensor will be tested by CSIC to be included into citizen science activities. Other plankton imaging instruments may be deployed within the regular monitoring programs of other institutes involved in T3.2. These deployments are not necessarily within the context of DTO-BioFlow.

The deployment of such sensors (acoustics, images, etc.) might need to be approved by the regional/national relevant authority, upon the country national defence strategy. Indeed, the [EU's Maritime Security Strategy \(EUMSS\)](#) is built upon closer collaboration within the EU, across regional and national levels. The Maritime Security Strategy promotes international peace and security, as well as respect for international rules and principles, while ensuring the sustainability of the oceans and the protection of biodiversity. A recent update is available on the [EC website](#).

Therefore, some European countries at the regional level deliver authorization for marine scientific research. As an example, in France, scientists will be asked to provide information on their research activities, specifically if instruments are deployed at sea: [Decree No. 2017-956 of 10 May 2017](#).

Recommendations:

Contact the regional/territorial maritime office to enquiry if permission is needed. This should be done at least one to two months before initiation of their research activities.

Protected areas: Identify the zone/area where research experiments will be carried out. Check if this area belongs to a specific protected area, and identify the relevant authorities to obtain a permit to conduct research activities.

Technology at sea: Identify the instruments/technology to be deployed at sea, Identify the zone/area where research experiments will be carried out, identify the relevant local authorities to see if a specific permit needs to be obtained.

5.3.7.7. Sensitive data and Artificial Intelligence Systems beyond DTO-BioFlow

It is recommended to compile all the above recommendations concerning sensitive data and their integration into AI systems into best practice document. These include: compliance with the Nagoya Protocol/ABS procedures, genetic/genomic or eDNA analyses, data obtained from tagged animals (tagging which require ethical approval), data obtained from samples of endangered species (CITES permits), etc.

This compilation of recommendations should be included in deliverable D3.2 "DTO-BioFlow best procedures and practice guidelines" and also submitted for consideration as a recognised best practice to the Ocean Best Practice System (OBPS).

The issue of integrating sensitive data (such as telemetry data) and disseminating it in real time (with an AIS system automatically integrating ocean data) is raised: How to integrate the data from endangered species into a model/AI System without compromising the geolocation of animals.

The two options identified so far are:

- Discuss with EDITO (in the context of WP4 & WP5) as to whether or not a technical solution to this issue can be developed.
- Create different identifiers (login, credential) for end users (at the interface level). Decisions as to who should have access to these sensitive data is beyond the competence of DTO-BioFlow partners but should be raised as an issue in a recommendation or in a relevant workshop with policy makers. This is a policymaker's decision. See WP4.

It is recommended that a stakeholder workshop be organized for the demonstrator use cases in the framework of WP4 to raise issues and alert decision-makers to this point and potentially co-create a solution.

5.4. WP4 - Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases the benefit of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring

This WP raises several ethical issues for which some solutions have been already been implemented:

- **Potential Human participation and personal data protection in EU & non EU countries:** the involvement of stakeholders and end-users, implies human participation and the protection of personal data, in both EU and non-EU countries.
- **Data management and security: issues regarding data providing geo-localisation of endangered species.**
- **The development of models to be integrated into a platform to support decision-making,** the models must be robust, verified and validated and bias should be identified. The final platform must guarantee, transparency about the limitation of the tool, explicability. **In case of development and/or use of AI systems/Machine Learning (ML) systems, the system should be trustworthy.**

5.4.1. Human participation and personal data protection

The technology developed in WP4 will not be applied to humans or personal data. All WP tasks (demonstrators) will develop a link to stakeholders in the academic, public and industry sector. This is to build an end-to-end value chain for marine biodiversity data. Stakeholders will primarily be chosen based on previous collaborations and existing trusted relations.

The consortium includes primarily research institutes from DTO-BioFlow consortium. New collaborations will be based on merits fitting the purpose of DTO-BioFlow as well as open-source culture.

Regarding Informed consent. Applications developed in WP4 may involve collection and analysis of training data provided by users, e.g., citizens. In all cases the consortium will ensure individuals can make informed decisions about the reuse of their images through authentication and authorisation functions, as well as by assigning data licenses to models, images, files, etc.

Recommendations

Remind each demo site about their institutional responsibility in protecting the personal data obtained from external stakeholders.

Ensure that WP4 is not storing personal data from citizens and remind demo sites that the personal data collected from citizens (during citizen sciences activities) must be protected and a Data Protection Officer at each Demo site should be informed on the collection and storage of these personal data.

Remind to Demo sites involving citizen science activities to include in the information sheet and informed consent a statement regarding the ownership of the data at the same time as obtaining their authorisation for using images.

5.4.2. Data management and security

Data collected and/or processed in WP4 can in some cases be sensitive, e.g., when including geographical references or when associated with endangered species. The consortium has a data security strategy, data management plans and procedures to deal with these risks, e.g., sensitive metadata will be omitted from analysis. Further storage and processing of all data is done exclusively on approved data infrastructures, typically academic research infrastructures who provide the highest data security standards and best possible conditions for implementing FAIR & CARE data principles.

Excellent initiative, which should be highlighted in the final WP2 best practices.

5.4.3. Regarding Animal welfare

Some applications developed in WP4 make valuable contributions to animal welfare in marine monitoring as they can replace destructive, invasive, harmful and pain-inflicting monitoring methods. Examples include trawl-based sampling, electric fishing, and cage trapping which can be replaced by passive visual, acoustic, or DNA-based monitoring.

Excellent point to be highlighted.

5.4.4. Trustworthy System

The consortium will mitigate ethical challenges by staying up-to-date with prevailing regulations, implementing methodologies that enable transparency in all analytical workflows, working in the open-source domain, advocating for FAIR & CARE data principles, and educate end users about ethical challenges and how we live up to them.

Which risks did you identify as relevant to your research activities?	Explain what are the issues (if any)
<u>Impact</u> examines the algorithm in terms of the effects it will have on people and property.	No issues anticipated.
<u>Appropriate Use</u> inspects the relationship between the data being used in the algorithm and the purpose for which the data was collected and perceptions of the anticipated use.	We will openly discuss relationships between data sources and application purpose, especially with end users.
<u>Accountability</u> surfaces how much involvement people have in the ongoing use of the algorithm, including whether automated decisions can be clearly explained to anyone.	We will document and demonstrate human-in-the loop applications and account for transparency of applications and potential decision outcomes.
<u>Bias</u> explores the underlying influence of the data and the people who helped build the algorithm	We will account for transparency of applications.

Recommendations for demo sites

With or without the use of AI, it is essential that the models/algorithms used in the decision support tool are reliable and explainable and that the sources of bias are identified. The models come also with many uncertainties, especially in the biological modelling and still involves some numerical approximation for being solved within the available computational power. Intrinsically, prediction uncertainties must be computed and considered.

To validate models, a benchmarking exercise could be carried out.

An in-depth analysis of the models used should be conducted to assess stability, robustness and data completeness and representativeness.

5.4.5. Future activities M18-M36 and recommendations

No information has been provided, but one can expect that the same activity will be pursued.

However, the question of how to integrate sensitive data (such as telemetry data) and disseminate them in real time (on an advanced DTO platform with an AI system automatically integrating ocean data into the model) arises as an issue beyond the duration of the DTO-BioFlow project. The question raised is: how can endangered species data be integrated into an AI model/system without compromising animal geolocation? This information is required by policy-makers. As mentioned, above, if a technological solution cannot be found, then another option to address this is the creation of different identifiers (login, credential) for end-users (at interface level), if feasible.

The process developed for ballast water at HELCOM could be presented as a “success story” or best practice as it includes an authentication authorisation infrastructure with certain level of credentials that addresses both national and regional concerns. Data products can be low or high resolution depending on the end user.

The European Commission defines Open Science as “an approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process” and advises that it should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

5.5. WP5 – Integration in DTO infrastructure

The objective of T5.1 is to link existing tools from EU projects like BioDT, Iliad, and EDITO to support continuous, high-quality data streaming in a scalable infrastructure, utilizing HPC clusters. These tools will enable seamless integration and reusability by automating workflows and simplifying access through R/Python libraries, abstracting the complexities of HPC and large-scale storage. Training and assistance will be provided to ensure sustainable use, enhancing accessibility and reliability in line with trustworthy system principles.

The objective of T5.2 is to align the set of requirements, design principles, service interface and data standards for cross project collaboration. This will ensure that DTO-BioFlow data streams are based on Digital Twin ready standards developed by other ongoing activities.

5.5.1. Trustworthy System

The consortium provided some information on the strategy applied to ensure a trustworthy decision support tool.

Which risks did you identify as relevant to your research activities?	Mitigation actions
<u>Impact</u> examines the algorithm in terms of the effects it will have on people and property.	In this activity no algorithm will be developed.
<u>Accountability</u> surfaces how much involvement people have in the ongoing use of the algorithm, including whether automated decisions can be clearly explained to anyone.	No new algorithms are being developed, instead, already existing algorithms are being applied in the DUC demonstrators. WP5 will facilitate the link between available tools and the DUC needs.
For these issues, explain which measures you developed for mitigation	
<i>Impact</i>	NA

<i>Appropriate Use</i>	Ensure the appropriate use of tools by providing training and guides on how the tools function and insights into the integration process
<i>Accountability</i>	NA
<i>Bias</i>	We are not responsible for the sourcing of the data, we work with the data that was provided to us by the other WPs.

Recommendations for demo sites

With or without the use of AI, it is essential that the models/algorithms used in the decision support tool are reliable and explainable and any sources of bias are identified. The models come also with many uncertainties, especially in the biological modelling and still involves some numerical approximation for being solved within the available computational power. Intrinsically, prediction uncertainties must be computed and considered. To validate models, a benchmarking exercise could be carried out.

An in-depth analysis of the models used should be conducted to assess stability, Robustness and Data completeness and representativeness.

It is also recommended (as discussed above) to investigate a solution to the issue of integrating endangered species data into an AI model/system without compromising animal geolocation.

Recommendations to WP5

Reminder for all: the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI by the High-Level Expert Group on AI² integrates the TRUSTWORTHY AI ASSESSMENT LIST (p26) also detailed on the EC website³.

Other guides have been made available in the share space on teams: Numeum: A practical guide to ethical AI⁴, The con fiance.ai programme⁵

Even if not responsible for the sourcing of data, the assessment of representativeness of these data should be carried out, to inform end-users.

5.5.2. Future activities M18-M36 and recommendations

WP5 will carry out some activities involving external stakeholders including organisation of workshops, interviews and online survey. Research activities in non-EU countries are anticipated but no details have been provided.

Recommendations regarding human participation and data protection

Before conducting an interview/survey, or organising a workshop you must,

- Read the deliverable D5.1 on the ethical recommendations provided while organising workshop.
- Define a clear recruitment process.
- Design an information sheet and informed consent, and translate if necessary.
- Contact the Data Protection Officer from your organisation for validation of the collection of data in your organisation.
- Collect signed informed consent from participants.
- Check that no personal data will be transferred between EU & non-EU countries.
- Conduct your survey/interview and secure informed consent.
- Pseudonymize personal data if necessary.

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-ai-self-assessment>

D1.6 Strategy for Addressing the Ethics M18

⁴ <http://ai-ethical.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/2022-SN-Guide-Methodo-IA-Ethiques-web-version.pdf/>

⁵ <https://www.confiance.ai/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/LivreBlanc-Con fiance.ai- Octobre2022.pdf>

NB: you legally engage your organisation in research activities, you must ensure that the collection, processing and storage of data are carried out in accordance with the provisions of your institution and at national level.

For workshops with policy-makers, a discussion should be initiated on how to manage the issue of integrating endangered species data into an AIS model/system without compromising animal geolocation. Is it acceptable to have different levels of access to sensitive information if a technological solution cannot be found?

For activities to be conducted in a non-EU country,

For activities carried out outside the EU, the activity must comply with the legal obligations of the country AND the activities must be allowed in at least one Member State.

NB: check with your Project Officer regarding research activities in Israel

For AIS/ML development,

The Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI by the High-Level Expert Group on AI⁶ integrates the TRUSTWORTHY AI ASSESSMENT LIST (p26) also detailed on the EC website⁷.

Other guides have been made available in the shared space on teams: Numeum: A practical guide to ethical AI⁸, The confiance.ai programme⁹

An in-depth analysis of the models used should be conducted to assess stability, Robustness and Data completeness and representativeness

6. Strategic plans – summary

A strategic plan is provided for each WP (see above) and can be summarised as follows:

6.1. Recommendations regarding human participation and data protection

Before conducting an interview/survey, or organising a workshop you must

- Read the deliverable D1.5 on the ethical recommendations provided while organising workshops.
- Define a clear recruitment process.
- Design an information sheet and informed consent, and translate if necessary.
- Contact the Data Protection Officer from your organisation for validation of the collection of data in your organisation.
- Collect and stored signed informed consent.
- Check that no personal data will be transferred between EU & non-EU countries or if it is the case ensure that is legal (see with your DPO).
- Conduct your survey/interview/workshop and secure informed consent.
- Pseudonymize personal data if necessary.
- Remind each demo site about their institutional responsibility in protecting the personal data obtained from external stakeholders. A Data Protection Officer at each Demo site/external partner should be informed on the collection and storage of these personal data (citizen science activities).

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-ai-self-assessment>

D1.6 Strategy for Addressing the Ethics M18

⁸ <http://ai-ethical.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/2022-SN-Guide-Methodo-IA-Ethiques-web-version.pdf>

⁹ <https://www.confiance.ai/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/LivreBlanc-Confiance.ai-Octobre2022.pdf>

- Remind to Demo sites involving citizen science activities to include in the information sheet and informed consent a statement regarding the ownership of the data at the same time that their authorisation for using images is sought.
- Include in the information sheets the rules concerning data ownership and the benefit-sharing actions implemented to recognize the participation of citizens in this collective scientific effort (perhaps a seminar, an article in the journal, T-shirt, certificate, final event, see <https://www.zooniverse.org/get-involved/volunteer> for further ideas).

NB: If you legally engage your organisation in research activities, you must ensure that the collection, processing and storage of data are carried out in accordance with the provisions of your institution and at national level.

While engaging citizen science activities with external organisations

Ensure that the external partners engaged in these citizen activities have a clear process for engaging citizen in the research activities:

- Recruitment process defined.
- Information sheet and obtained informed consent from citizen.
- Explanation of the safety rules.
- Protection of their personal data.
- Define the ownership of data.
- Implement benefit actions for citizens (<https://www.zooniverse.org/get-involved/volunteer>).

Ensure that the external partners that are collecting sediment or sea water samples for genetic (including eDNA) analysis are in compliance with the Nagoya Protocol and applicable ABS regulations. Pay specific attention for citizen activities conducted in low-middle income countries.

6.2. For activities to be conducted in a non-EU country

For activities carried out outside the EU, the activity must comply with the legal obligations of the country AND the activities must be allowed in at least one Member State.

NB: check with your Project Officer regarding research activities in Israel.

6.3. Data sourcing

Data obtained from existing data collected through fish tagging:

Contact the data providers to ask them to confirm they obtained an ethics approval for these experimentations

Genetic data

- **For samples compliant with the NP/ABS regulation** (such as those available via [EMO BON](#)): start the ingestion from material sample data. The data providers should confirm the compliance.
- **For genetic data obtained from samples for which compliance with the ABC regulation is unclear** and for samples collected in the framework of long-term time series observatories:
 - o Contact the responsible people from each observatory and ask them to confirm the compliance of the samples or not. (The samples collected during the Ocean Sampling Day and during Tara expeditions are known to (should be) be compliant with ABS regulation).

- **For samples collected before the NP entered into force (2014-10-12), at EU level**, a relevant contact point at the EU level should be sought to ask if permission is needed. The integration of such data is acceptable if the origin of the data is European.
 - **For samples collected before the NP entered into force (2014-10-12), outside of EU waters**, contact the NFP of the country in question to ask whether the consortium needs authorization to use the data. NFPs will require an explanation of the purpose of the research activities, how the data will be used, etc. Ask if permission is needed; particular attention should be paid to low- and middle-income countries outside the EU. The NCPs are available on the websites provided in D5.1.
 - **If the origin of data/samples is unknown**, try to identify the data provider and contact/ask them to fill in a table with related information (a template is available for the partners via the MS Teams/SharePoint environment, an overview of the template information has been provided in D5.1). **If samples are coming from low- and middle-income countries, the NCPs must be contacted to get the authorization to use the data.** If the origin of the data/samples remains unknown these samples/data should not be used.
- **For data obtained from endangered or sensitive species occurrences outside the EU waters.**
- These samples, if collected in non-EU waters and transferred to EU, must be compliant with CITES
- Contact the responsible people to ask them to confirm that samples were obtained in compliance with CITES.
 - Or
 - Identify the species and check their presence on Appendix I, II.
 - Identify where the samples come from: EU, non-EU, EEZ, high seas.
 - Contact the responsible people to ensure that samples were obtained in compliance with CITES.
 - Consult the CITES ¹⁰ website if needed.

6.4. For AIS/ML development, models integration

Read the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI by the High-Level Expert Group on AI ¹¹ which integrates the TRUSTWORTHY AI ASSESSMENT LIST (p26) also detailed on the EC website ¹². Other guides have been made available in the shared space on teams: Numeum: A practical guide to ethical AI ¹³, The con fiance.ai programme ¹⁴.

An in-depth analysis of the models used should be conducted to assess stability, Robustness and Data completeness and representativeness.

Recommendations for demo sites

With or without the use of AI, it is essential that the models/algorithms used in the decision support tool are reliable and explainable and bias are identified. The models come also with mainly uncertainties, especially in the biological modelling and still involves some numerical approximation for being solved within the available computational power. Intrinsically, prediction uncertainties must be computed and considered.

To validate models, a benchmarking exercise could be carried out.

An in-depth analysis of the models used should be conducted to assess stability, Robustness and Data completeness and representativeness.

¹⁰ <https://cites.org/eng>

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

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¹³ <http://ai-ethical.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/2022-SN-Guide-Methodo-IA-Ethiques-web-version.pdf/>

¹⁴ <https://www.confiance.ai/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/LivreBlanc-Confiance.ai-October2022.pdf>

6.5. Recommendations for new biologging activities

1. Determine if tagging is appropriate.
2. Consider alternative methods for addressing research questions.
3. Review relevant existing data for the species and area of consideration.
4. Ensure that there is a scientific or conservation justification for obtaining new data and that those data are best provided by tags.
5. Follow best practices of research design.
6. Develop the research plan with animal welfare as a high priority.
7. Evaluate equipment options and choose the instrument and attachment that provide the data needed.
8. As much as possible, ascertain required samples sizes and statistical approaches in advance, obtaining expert advice if needed.
9. Tag the fewest number of individuals necessary in the least invasive and impactful manner possible to achieve the project goals.
10. Prepare adequately for fieldwork.
11. Conduct a thorough risk assessment in advance.
12. Prepare for unexpected risks to the safety of animals and humans.
13. Ensure the capture/tagging team is trained in the safe and proper procedures for boat approaches (and capture-release techniques if required) and use of tagging equipment.
14. Comply with all applicable local, national and international legal requirements.
15. Obtain review and approval by an animal ethics committee, even if not locally required.

6.6. Recommendations regarding deployment of technology at sea

1. Contact the regional/territorial maritime office to enquire if permission is needed. This should be done at least one to two months before initiation of their research activities.
2. **Protected areas:** Identify the zone/area where research experiments will be carried out. Check if this area belongs to a specific protected area, and identify the relevant authorities to obtain a permit to conduct research activities.
3. **Technology at sea:** Identify the instruments/technology to be deployed at sea, identify the zone/area where research experiments will be carried out, identify the relevant local authorities to see if a specific permit needs to be obtained.

7. Conclusions

This current version of the DTO-BioFlow Ethics Strategy follows discussions and meetings between the Ethics Advisor and WP leaders together with the analysis of the ethics-self assessment produced for each WP. The aim is to better define the ethical issues and mitigation actions, with recommendations provided. Even if some of the ethical issues detailed in D1.5 do not apply directly to WP2, it is essential that the important recommendations are included to address the identified barriers such as Nagoya Protocol/ABS regulation or CITES compliance and use of data obtained from tagged fish or any solution developed within the project to protect endangered species.

